

Ethical Review Form

(Version 27.06.2019)

This Ethical Review Form should be completed for every research study that involves human participants or personally identifiable data and should be submitted before potential participants are approached to take part in the research study.

Part 1: General Study Information

1	Project title and project number	Current practices for the development and maintenance of the digital twin software artifacts
2	Researcher name and email	Hossain Muhammad Muctadir (h.m.muctadir@tue.nl)
3	Supervisor(s)	Prof.dr. Mark van den Brand (m.g.j.v.d.brand@tue.nl) Dr.ir. Loek Cleophas (l.g.w.a.cleophas@tue.nl)
4	Faculty/department	Software Engineering & Technology cluster, Department of Mathematics & Computer Science
5	Research location	Online or at TU/e campus
6	Research period (start/end date)	August 2021 – June 2022
7	Funding agency	This research is part of the Digital Twin project which is a TTW-Perspective Program co-funded by NWO
8	[If Applicable] Study is part of an educational course with code:	N/A
9	[If Applicable] Proposal already approved by external Ethical Review Board: Add name, date of approval, and contact details of the ERB	N/A
10	Short description of the research question	<p>With the increasing popularity of smart manufacturing, also known as Industry 4.0, digital twins (DT) have received significant attention both in academia and industry. A DT is a pairing of a physical asset and a corresponding virtual entity where the later mimics the former in terms of physical as well as behavioral properties. Although the concept of DT is about two decades old, it is becoming a key technology only recently. Therefore, there is no widely accepted standardization around DTs. As a result, organizations are using their own set of tools and methodologies for developing their own DT. In this interview research, we want to get more insight into the usage, development, and maintenance of the various DTs by answering the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How various software artifacts used in digital twins are developed and maintained? Is there any identifiable trend in the usage and development of DTs?
11	Description of the research method	<p>During this study, we plan to perform a series of semi-structured interviews. This means that the topic of the interview and a set of related questions will be predetermined. However, the questions may not be strictly followed, rather they will act as guidance for the conversation. The interview questions are related to the above-mentioned research questions. These interviews will be conducted with individuals who are direct user or developer of a digital twin.</p> <p>The information collected/recorded during the interview will be anonymized and analyzed to answer the mentioned research questions.</p>

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12	Description of the research population, exclusion criteria	We intend to interview people who have significant technical insight on a digital twin that is being used in research and/or to solve industrial use cases.
13	Description of the measurements and/or stimuli/treatments	The purpose of the interviews is to learn from the experiences of the interviewees and use that knowledge for further analysis. Therefore, we do not have any plan to perform any measurements or use any stimuli during the interview.
14	Number of participants	Approximately 20
15	Explain why the research is socially important. What benefits and harm to society may result from the study?	The outcome of this study will be used to identify potential high-impact areas in the development of digital twins and focus future research activities in those areas. Digital Twins, in high-tech systems, but also in the life sciences, have the potential to impact society in many ways, by allowing the use of (real-time) sensor data to analyze and improve systems and entities. The discussions during the interviews may already lead to increased insight for participants and interviewers, but the main benefits are expected to arise from the research to be undertaken because of the directions we will set based on the interview results.
16	Describe the way participants will be recruited	The participants will be chosen for their role in research or development of a digital twin, whether used in research or in industrial use-cases. The initial set of participants will be recruited by approaching our research and industrial partners. From this initial set we will snowball, by asking for a small number of referrals from each respondent. This process will continue until saturation has been reached.
17	Provide a brief statement of the risks you expect for the participants or others involved in the research or educational activity and explain. Take into consideration any personal data you may gather and privacy issues.	During this interview, we will discuss technical details of a digital twin and the interviewees' involvement with it. As a result, the discussion will include personally identifiable information that we will discard prior to any further processing. Technical discussion may include details that should not be made publicly available. During the processing of the gathered information, we will identify and discard such proprietary information.

Part 2: Checklist for Minimal Risk

		Yes	No
1	Does the study involve participants who are particularly vulnerable or unable to give informed consent? (e.g. children, people with learning difficulties, patients, people receiving counselling, people living in care or nursing homes, people recruited through self-help groups)		X
2	Are the participants, outside the context of the research, in a dependent or subordinate position to the investigator (such as own children or own students)?		X
3	Will it be necessary for participants to take part in the study without their knowledge and consent at the time? (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places)		X
4	Will the study involve actively deceiving the participants? (e.g. will participants be deliberately falsely informed, will information be withheld from them or will they be misled in such a way that they are likely to object or show unease when debriefed about the study)		X

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5	Will the study involve discussion or collection of personal data? (e.g. name, address, phone number, email address, IP address, BSN number, location data) or will the study collect and store videos, pictures, or other identifiable data of human subjects?. Please check the FAQ's on the intranet . If yes: please follow the procedure . Make sure you perform a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and make a Data Management Plan if necessary and let the data steward check it. Please attach these documents with this form (see part 5; enclosures)	X	
6	Will participants be asked to discuss or report sexual experiences, religion, alcohol or drug use, or suicidal thoughts, or other topics that are highly personal or intimate?		X
7	Will participating in the research be burdensome? (e.g. requiring participants to wear a device 24/7 for several weeks, to fill in questionnaires for hours, to travel long distances to a research location, to be interviewed multiple times)?		X
8	May the research procedure cause harm or discomfort to the participant in any way? (e.g. causing pain or more than mild discomfort, stress, anxiety or by administering drinks, foods, drugs)		X
9	Will blood or other (bio)samples be obtained from participants (e.g. also external imaging of the body)?		X
10	Will financial inducement (other than reasonable expenses and compensation for time) be offered to participants?		X
11	Will the experiment involve the use of physical devices that are not 'CE' certified?		X

Important:

If you answered all questions with "no", you can skip parts 3 - 4 and go directly to part 5. Check which documents you need to enclose and continue with signature and submission.

If you answered one or more questions with "yes", please continue with parts 3 – 5.

Part 3: Study Procedures and Sample Size Justification

1	Elaborate on all boxes answered with "yes" in part 2. Describe how you safeguard any potential risk for the research participant.	Box 5: The personal data that we intend to explicitly collect are name, email, workplace, and role at workplace. These data will be temporarily stored using TU/e infrastructure (i.e., TU/e GitLab, Microsoft Stream/OneDrive instance of TU/e) with strict access control. The name and email will only be used to contact the interviewee. Information regarding the workplace will be used to understand the depth of the technical knowledge of the subject regarding the digital twin. The audio and video recording may contain other personal information. This information will be discarded during the transcription process. Moreover, the recordings will be removed no later than June 2022.
2	Describe and justify the number of participants you need for this research or educational activity. Also justify the number of observations you need, taking into account the risks and benefits	We do not expect to interview more than 20 individuals. The participants are chosen for their involvement in development or research in digital twins. In this study, we intend to find patterns related to the development and maintenance of digital twins. Our initial research has shown that a sample size of 20 is sufficient to find such patterns.

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Part 4: Data and Privacy Statement

1	Explain whether your data are completely anonymous, or if they will be de-identified (pseudonymized or anonymized) and explain how.	We will discard any personal information from audio recording during transcription. All recorded information (i.e., video, audio) will be stored using TU/e infrastructure for at most one year. Afterwards, they will be deleted.
2	Who will have access to the data?	<p>This study is part of the work package 3 of the digital twin [1] research project. The research activities of this work package are being carried out by the following personnel from the Eindhoven University of Technology and Tilburg University. Therefore, they will have access to all information related to this study.</p> <p>Hossain Muhammad Muctadir (h.m.muctadir@tue.nl) David Manrique Negrin (d.a.manrique.negrin@tue.nl) Dr.ir. Loek Cleophas (l.g.w.a.cleophas@tue.nl) Prof.dr. Mark van den Brand (m.g.j.v.d.brand@tue.nl) Raghavendran Gunasekaran (R.Gunasekaran@tilburguniversity.edu) Prof.dr.ir. Boudewijn Haverkort (b.r.h.m.haverkort@tilburguniversity.edu)</p> <p>[1] 'Home - Digital Twin Research'. <i>Digital Twin</i>, https://www.digital-twin-research.nl/. Accessed 17 Aug. 2021.</p>
3	Will you store personal information that will allow participants to be identified from their data? See <u>VSNU draft</u> .	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes, and I declare I will follow the general data protection regulation (GDPR).
4	Will you share de-identified data (e.g., upon publication in a public repository)?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes, and I will inform participants about how their data will be shared and ask consent to share their data. I will, to the best of my knowledge and ability, make sure the data do not contain information that can identify participants.

Part 5: Closures and Signatures

1	Enclosures (tick if applicable): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Informed consent form; <input type="checkbox"/> Informed consent form for other agencies when the research is conducted at a location (such as a school); <input type="checkbox"/> Text used for ads (to find participants); <input type="checkbox"/> Text used for debriefings; <input type="checkbox"/> Approval other research ethics committee; 	
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	<input type="checkbox"/> The survey the participants need to complete, or a description of other measurements; <input type="checkbox"/> Any other information which might be relevant for decision making by ERB; <input type="checkbox"/> Data Protection Impact Assessment checked by the privacy officer <input type="checkbox"/> Data Management Plan checked by a data steward	
2	Signature(s) Signature(s) of researcher(s) Date: Signature research supervisor (if applicable) Date:	Hossain Muhammad Muctadir August 17, 2021